

Can Vegetarian Diet Reverse Diabetes?

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Abidjan (Cote d'Ivoire): May 2012

English version: November 2016

Abstract:

Diabetes is a metabolic disease that continues to grow. However, the incurable nature of the disease is questioned within the scientific community. The author examines the work of two experts concerning the cure of diabetes by a vegetarian diet.

Keywords:

Diabetes, vegetarian diet, cure.

Diabetes is one of these "new diseases" that continue, especially since the 50's, to progress thanks to the growth of adverse health lifestyle and diet. It is generally considered incurable in all its forms, at most we can substantially limit the effects. Also do we see many patients sentenced to insulin injections or absorption of tablets for life. Efforts are made and are visible to grant sick more facilities for their treatment and their social care. However, the incurable nature of the disease is questioned within the scientific world. The work of several specialists are indicative of the reversibility of diabetes by special treatment, vegetarian diet.

Before giving the floor to one of them, Dr. Hans Diehl¹, it should be noted that the results obtained by him and his team are likely to give real hope to the victims of this disease considered incurable. These findings are supportive of other voices in the medical world who profess a therapeutic based on the reform of lifestyle and nutritional intake.

¹ Dr. Hans Diehl is an American specialist in cardiovascular epidemiology. He is the director of the Institute of Medicine on the Lifestyles of Loma Linda University (California). He is the founder of the health program *Complete Health Improvement Program* (CHIP).

Let us now hear Dr. Diehl expose to us his proven theses²:

"... Now look at the question of why there are so many cases of diabetes and what can we do to reverse diabetes? For many years, we opted for a diet consisting mostly of fat because we had the mistaken opinion that diabetics cannot assimilate carbohydrates, sugar. We airplanes until then not made the distinction between simple carbohydrates and complex carbohydrates; between sugar and starch. [...] And if a person cannot consume sugar, we said, then he must consume a lot of fat and protein. This was unfortunately the guideline for the treatment of diabetics. In 1921, 70% of the diet of diabetics was made up of fat, so that these poor were dying of arteriosclerosis and heart disease. [...]"

For Dr. Diehl, like many other specialists, the fundamental cause underlying the progression of diabetes is the excessive amount of fat in a western-style food culture that tends to globalize. 40% of fat in this diet are well above the 5 to 15% of fat required in a normal diet.

"What follows, he says, comes from a company large-scale study by the Adventist Church, which followed 30,000 people. Among the latter, vegetarians had very little diabetes, meat eaters had it 400 times more. These findings confirm that, since the meat is very rich in fat, it is the fat that determines the results. Globally, we can estimate that in twenty or thirty years ahead there will be a significant increase in cases of diabetes, as more and more people around the world are adopting a lifestyle and a Western-style diet.

In 1933, Dr. Rabinowitch, of Montreal, in Canada, studied the treatment of diabetes and was able to verify the findings already obtained with people with a simple vegetarian diet very low in fat. In 1955, Dr. Inder Singh wanted to verify these results with a diet of natural foods containing only 1% of fat or vegetarian diets. There were 80 diabetics on insulin. Among them, 50 were able to stop insulin in six weeks.

We still have other results. In the same way, in the British medical journal *Lancet*, one could read that with a diet low in fat, the insulin that the body produces normally becomes active in diabetics, who can return to normal health within a few weeks. [...]"

Hans Diehl and others are in that in perfect agreement with Dr. Guillaume Guelpa, a Franco-Italian doctor who trumpeted on the subject at the beginning of the twentieth century³ :

"... Recently, a great teacher now retired, doing lessons on one of the most serious complications of diabetes, diabetic gangrene, especially drew the attention of listeners on

² Extracts from the conference by Dr. Diehl at the 7th European Vegetarian Congress, held in July 1999 in Widnau (Switzerland). Full text available at URL www.vegetarismus.ch/pdf/b13.pdf .

³ Extracts of text entitled *Désintoxication organique et Régime végétarien*, conference by Dr. Guelpa at the Vegetarian Society of France, 11 April 1911. Entire document available at URL www.jeune-et-randonnee.pagesperso-orange.fr/Guelpaocr.htm .

the need to fight against the weakness of patients and support their strengths by raising the rations of meat and eggs after removing all starchy food. He did not realize that the feeling of weakness of his patients was the expression of the poisoning, which is caused by acid waste and sugar produced in excess and not eliminated because of the depletion of hematopoietic organs, and by his misinterpretation he would increase overwork those already failing organs. [...] "

For Dr. Guelpa, fortifying diabetics by the cramming of meat is a dangerous practice that cannot bear comparison with the naturist rehab where vegetarian food figures prominently.

"In a communication, he says, I made recently in the Medical Society, *The Cure of Diabetes*, I have shown that in this disease, which is gravity, the key element is the tissue acid poisoning, not overproduction of sugar excreted in the urine ..." Guelpa prioritizes if not identifies acidosis of tissues as the key factor in the progression of the disease in the patient's body. In doing so, he sees in the sugar overproduction the appropriate way to the discharge of meat products's toxins, "because, he said, this overproduction, rather than being the danger in the disease, is on the contrary the fix, the positive element, in the same way as profuse watery drinks necessitated by thirst, are the fix, the beneficial element, when the body is intoxicated by excess of salt ingested in food. Indeed, the exaggeration of salt in tissues is harmful to their cellular function and abundant watery drinks are needed for rapid removal, for washing, of this chlorinated intoxication. In diabetes, acid poisoning, mostly from meat products finds in the sugar solutions the most favorable environment for its elimination."

In light of the treatment methods stemming from this original premise, Dr. Guelpa could ease in minimum time many diabetics, who see to submit to "a small vegetarian diet, with removal of meat products, eggs and strong drinks" as well as "periods of fasting and purging at intervals more and more distant, to be always certain of success." Not without lucidly warned that "this healing can take place if it is the true diabetes, not a diabetic symptomatic manifestation of an incurable disease (cancer, tuberculosis, brain tumors, etc.)."

Dr. Guelpa confides then have had an interesting opportunity to accredit his theses: it was after a meeting with Dr. Coyon, four days after the above communication. During the conversation, which soon was directed towards the ideas of Dr. Guelpa about diabetes, he noted that his colleague, "while recognizing the benefits of detox", expressed doubt as to the invariably complete character of Guelpa's results. Also at the request

of the latter, Dr. Coyon entrusted to him one of his patients, 65-years old, son of parents dead of diabetes, undermined by the same evil that was completed, so quite inopportune, by advanced "inflammation ankylosing" of the right knee. It was an opportunity for Guelpa to prove the high therapeutic value of the vegetarian diet associated with dietary restriction completed of salt purges. Here is, for example, the patient's menu after a few days of fasting and purges based on sodium sulphate: morning, a fruit and a cup of coffee; noon, greens, abundant salad, 30 grams of bread and a fruit; evening, a julienne soup, green vegetables, 30 grams of bread and a fruit, watery drinks at will.

The works of Guillaume Guelpa and, more recently, Hans Diehl and other experts speak for themselves. The reversal of diabetes by a "simple" food reform under medical assistance is worthwhile and just boost the already commendable efforts of research related to medical monitoring of patients. Best, assisted vegetarian diet, coupled with insulin treatment is likely to restore the patient within weeks. This means a final judgment of the management of this hormone after treatment.

However, these findings must be thorough and widespread by research. Hygienist cures are still greeted with reserve in some quarters. Witness the unfortunate but understandable reaction of this social worker in Cote d'Ivoire, who quickly dissuaded a diabetic child's parent to follow him by a naturopath⁴, which could have been him much good. A Christian sage said, "Prove all things; hold fast that which is good." Healthy collaboration between various medical schools is not to discourage but to promote. The stakes being wellness individual and public health.

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⁴ In *Fraternité Matin*, Ivorian newspaper of general information, no. 14235, 8 May 2012, p.2.